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“NO STONES UNTURNED”

Through storm and vigour he walks on his own,
With toughened hand, but heart of gold.
No peak so high, no river so wide,
Could shake the strength he holds inside.

He speaks in deeds, resonant voice,
Each tread he move is firm, rock-solid and profound.
No mission too great, no bridge too far-off,
He whittles his fate, he bears no fear but utters pray'r

The world may cast trial, the winds may grumble,
Yet in his eyes, no fear nor scowl.
In every test, he stands his ground,
No truth is lost, no path unfound.

He never leave every stone unturned, he gibes so deep,
No secret left for time to hold.
With iron will and whetted heart and mind,
No thread of fate is left behind.

No rest, no pause, no backward glance,
Through tempest come and sun raises high, he makes his stance.
His sweat, his blood, his silent creed,
A man of strength, a man of deed.,

And up to now the echoes of his legend grows.
A great command still keeps its glow,
Not to forget how well he lead
The people bend with trust and faith,
For no stones unturned remains till then.